

MECHANICAL EFFECTS OF THE INJECTION-CVD NANOSTRUCTURATION OF CARBON-FIBRE COMPOSITES INVESTIGATED BY BUNDLE TENSILE TEST AND DMA

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ABSTRACT

As already studied by a few authors, the interlayer inclusion of VACNTs forests in laminated composite parts by injection-CVD process appears to be a promising way to improve their mechanical properties, and open the paths towards new applications such as ballistic armors. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the effects of the injection-CVD synthesis on the mechanical strength and more specifically the interlaminar shear strength of the nanostructured composites.

The fibre bundle test will help to determine the mechanical effects of the various thermal treatments required to enable the CVD growth of VACNT on 3K carbon fibre threads. During conventional VACNTs forest growth the carbon fibres are pre-treated with a SiO₂ substrate deposition at 500 °C before a catalytic growth at 850 °C. For these experimental tests we will consider 4 different configurations to investigate the impact of each step on the mechanical properties : (i) untreated fabric, (ii) pre-treatment at 500 °C with SiO₂ coating, (iii) pre-treatment at 850 °C to remove sizing and (iv) long stage at 850 °C with CNT growth. With determining the number and the diameter of carbon fibres in each bundle sample, a repeatable and reproducible method can be introduced to measure the young's modulus of the carbon fibres and to estimate its variation.

The dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) gives concrete variations of some dynamic mechanical properties of laminated composites nanostructured by VACNTs inclusion. For these measurements, conventional and nanostructured composites consisting of 4 layers with ±45° orientation were moulded. The preforms are stacked in a RTM mould and processed with conventional vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding (VARTM) of Hexcel RTM6 resin system. This approach allows the production of large nanostructured composite samples without interfering with the VACNTs orientation. The short-term objective is therefore to investigate the influence of the micromechanical properties on the impact performance of the produced nanostructured composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

The damages initiation and propagation on composite plates are affected by several mechanisms dominated by delamination, fibre breakage and matrix cracking at high velocity impacts [1,2]. The homogeneous dispersion of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in thermoplastic or thermoset resins had limited effect on ballistic performances [3-5], but has opened the way for the structuration by the interlaminar inclusion of vertically aligned carbon nanotubes (VACNTs) forest. Mechanical studies on moulded composites with VACNTs inclusion reported a spectacular increase of the fracture toughness G_{IC} (0.95 to 4.26 kJ.m⁻²) and G_{IIC} (0.091 to 0.140 kJ.m⁻²) through the interlaminar nanostructuring of a two-layered carbon/epoxy moulded composite plate [6]. An increase of G_{IC} from 0.21 to 0.53 kJ.m⁻² and of G_{IIC} from 0.35 to 1.1 kJ.m⁻² for a 24-layer composite laminate with a central CNT interlaminar inclusion by transfer printing was also reported [7]. The grafting of CNTs on carbon fibres by CVD in vacuum has showed an improvement of the carbon filaments' strength in single filament tensile test [8]. While the grafting of CNTs on single carbon fibre filaments may result in a better interface between the fibre and resin, this technique would be complicated and expensive to upscale to a composite part. The growth of VACNT forests directly on a carbon fibre fabric allows to target the inclusion of CNTs at the interlaminar interface, where the increased mechanical properties are desired, while maintaining ease of handling and impregnation. This technique was extended to the production of preforms of up to 280 x 280 mm and opens the way for application of traditional mechanical testings on large nanostructured composites.

Manufacturing conditions, interfacial shear properties and orientation of the carbon nanotubes in composite plates are major determinant for improving mechanical properties. The aim of our study is to characterize the effects of the VACNTs growth by injection-CVD process on carbon fabrics, in a large mechanical test campaign, including bundle tensile test on CNTs grafted carbon fibres and dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) on nanostructured carbon/epoxy composite plates, those constitute a preliminary step toward ballistic impact tests on large nanostructured composites armour (110 x 110 mm). The injection-CVD process requires a preliminary treatment of the carbon fibres with a SiO₂ sub-layer deposition at 500°C for a few minutes, and a catalytic decomposition of organic precursors (ferrocene/toluene) at 850°C for a duration depending on the expected growth length of the VACNTs forest (few minutes) [9]. The resulting CNTs present a radial orientation around carbon filaments exposed to the vapor deposition. Carbon fibre bundles and woven carbon fabrics are treated and selected in each step of injection-CVD process for bundle tensile tests and DMA, respectively. 4 different treatments are considered for bundle tensile tests : i) as-received carbon fibres, ii) pre-treated with SiO₂ sub-layer deposition, iii) heated at 850°C for complete desizing and iv) treated with VACNTs growth. The Young's modulus of carbon filaments in tensile test is determined using the Fibre Bundle Model (FBM) [10,11]. For DMA tests the woven carbon fabrics are moulded with aerospace grade epoxy resin in vacuum assisted transfer moulding (VARTM), to produce 2 mm thick composite plates with 4 layers at ± 45° fibres orientation. The dynamical properties are investigated by determining the storage modulus of three different samples: i) with as-received woven fabrics, ii) pre-treated with SiO₂ sub-layer deposition, and iii) with nanostructured woven fabrics.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

All the fibre bundles and the woven fabrics come from a 3K 5-harness satin carbon fabric roll, woven with HTA40 Toho Tenax® carbon fibres. The physical and mechanical properties of the HTA40 fibres are listed in the Table 1. The fabrics and single fibre bundles were treated at Francis Perrin Laboratory, CEA, France, and a few samples were taken at each step of the injection-CVD process. The growth of VACNTs requires 3 successive treatments : At first, the carbon fabric or the carbon fibre bundle was heated at 500°C for complete desizing, a SiO₂ sub-layer was then deposited on the exposed surface of the carbon fibres, before the VACNTs growth at 850°C for few minutes by catalytic decomposition of organic precursors (toluene/ferrocene). The length of the CNTs is comprised between 20 µm and 110 µm, depending on the sample's exposure to the vapor deposition

Preparation of composite specimens for DMA

The composite specimens are composed of 4 layers of carbon fabric at an orientation of $\pm 45^\circ$. The 110x70 mm preforms were infused by VARTM, in a solid mould set with a 2mm cavity thickness using a steel spacer. All the samples were prepared together in one single injection, to ensure identical cure level of the resin. The areal density of the carbon fabric was measured for each nature of treatment to determine the volume fraction of carbon fibres and, in the case of nanostructured specimens, calculate the volume fraction of the VACNTs (see Table 3). The mould cavity was evacuated to a vacuum level of 4 mbar; due to the significant decrease of the longitudinal permeability caused by the VACNTs growth [12], to ensure complete impregnation in a timely manner, the injection pressure was set to 2 bars. The preforms were moulded with HexFlow® RTM6 using the manufacturer's recommended parameters (degassing at 70°C for 15 minutes, injection at 80°C with a mould temperature of 120°C). The composites were then cured at 180 °C for 2 hours and examined using optical microscopy (Figure 3).

Nature of the sample	Carbon fibre bundle	Composite plate
Mechanical test	Bundle tensile test	Dynamic mechanical analysis
Nature of the fibres	3K HTA40 Toho Tenax®	3K HTA40 Toho Tenax®
Specimen preparation	Impregnation of the fibre bundle extremities	4 layers moulded with $\pm 45^\circ$ fibres orientation in VARTM, epoxy resin
Test specimens	i) Raw bundle	i) 4 raw plies
	ii) Pre-treated with SiO ₂ deposition (500°C)	ii) 4 plies pre-treated with SiO ₂ deposition (500°C)
	iii) Desized (850°C)	iii) 4 plies with VACNTs growth (850°C)
	iv) VACNTs growth (850°C)	-

Table 2 : Nature and treatment of the tested specimens

2.2 Test Procedure*Bundle tensile test*

Bundle tensile tests were performed on a tensile test machine equipped with wedge action grips, and were conducted under laboratory environment at room temperature (21°C). The specimen was first vertically clamped at its aluminium end with the upper grip. The second end was vertically adjusted and clamped in the lower grip. The fibre bundles were lubricated with unflavoured petroleum to prevent fibre-to-fibre frictional forces that would act in addition to the tensile force. A pre-load of 5 N was applied before attaching an extensometer on the aluminium tubes (Figure 2) the length of the fibre bundle between the two aluminium tubes was precisely measured with a calliper gauge. In case of nanostructured samples, a slack transparent polyethylene film was placed around the aluminium tubes to prevent dissemination of carbon nanotubes after breakage. Extension at a crosshead speed of 1 $\mu\text{m/s}$ was applied until complete failure of the fibre bundle and a load-strain curve was plotted using the strain measured by the extensometer. To calculate the stress, the number and the section of the carbon filaments were determined from micrographs by image analysis with ImageJ®.

Figure 2 : a) Experimental set-up for a) fibre bundle testing and b) DMA testing; c) sectionnal view of the nanostructured preforms configuration

DMA test

The overall dimensions of the composite specimen were controlled with a Vernier calliper and corrected with a precision grinder (reported in Table 3). The specimens were tested in traction-compression mode using a dynamic mechanical analyzer MetraVib® DMA⁺¹⁰⁰ with isothermal cycle (room temperature at 24.7 °C) and a fixed frequency of 0.6 Hz. The composite sample was first clamped in the upper grip and its alignment was controlled with calibration blocks. The test length and width varied from 17 mm to 30 mm and from 0.7 mm to 1.2 mm, respectively. The oscillation amplitude was set to 1 µm, and the cycle time is fixed at 300 s.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The micrographs of cross sections of the composite samples (Figure 3) clearly highlight the interlaminar inclusion of the VACNTs and its preferred orientation in the direction normal to the carbon fabrics. The thickness of the VACNTs forest on the carbon fibres is noticeable at 100 µm and make contact with the upper and the lower ply at some points (Figure 3 b). The volume fraction of the VACNTs was determined by successive weighting of the preforms and the composite samples. The volume fractions of the carbon fibres and the VACNTs for DMA samples are reported in the Table 3.

DMA specimen	Volume fraction		Dimensions thickness x length x width [mm]
	Fibres [%]	VACNTs [%]	
Raw carbon fabric ($291 \pm 4 \text{ g/m}^2$)	33 ± 2	-	2.03 x 23.03 x 0.74
Pre-treated with SiO ₂ deposition ($204 \pm 3 \text{ g/m}^2$)	23 ± 2	-	2.06 x 34.42 x 0.85
Treated with VACNTs growth ($341 \pm 3 \text{ g/m}^2$)	32 ± 2	18 ± 2	2.02 x 21.22 x 0.72

Table 3: Volume fraction of carbon fibres and VACNTs reinforcement in DMA samples

Figure 3 : Optical micrographs of the slicer view for the composite specimens.

a) as-received carbon fabrics and b) nanostructured carbon fabrics

The carbon fabric desizing resulting from the pre-treatment at 850°C resulted in a noticeable decrease of its areal density of 2.7% ($291 \pm 4 \text{ g/m}^2$ to $281 \pm 3 \text{ g/m}^2$). The SiO_2 sub-layer deposition stage at 500°C results in a significant weight loss of the specimens (due to partial oxidation of the carbon fibres in contact with the organometallic precursor (tetraethylorthosilicate)). Given the fixed cavity thickness of the mould, the variation of areal weight has a direct impact on the volume fraction (Table 3) and on the mechanical properties of the composite specimens.

The Young's Modulus of the carbon filaments was determined from the load-strain curve obtained for the bundle tensile tests (Figure 4) with a statistical model describing the distribution of the filaments breakage in the bundle and its progress depending on the strain ε [%] (Equation (1)). The strain was deduced from the elongation of the extensometer compared to the test length. The behaviour of the

bundle is driven by the number of filaments N_0 , the filament's section A_f [m²], the value of the Young's modulus of the individual filaments E_f [GPa] and the normal distribution law $S(\varepsilon)$ according to the equation (1):

$$F_b = N_0 \cdot A_f \cdot E_f \cdot \varepsilon \cdot S(\varepsilon) \quad (1)$$

Figure 4: Load-strain curve of bundle tensile test with different treatment regimes

In the linear portion of the curve, the Young's Modulus is deduced from the values of N_0 , A_f and E_f ($S(\varepsilon) = 0$). The values for the mechanical properties for untreated carbon fibres determined by bundle tensile tests differ with the producer's data (Table 1), owing to the test procedure. The results show that the Young's modulus and tensile strength for untreated filaments are 168.2 GPa and 1984 MPa, respectively (Figure 5). The pre-treatments have led to an increase of the elongation at break from 1.2% to 1.8%. The SiO₂ deposition at 550°C results in an increase of the tensile strength, gaining 7% (1984 to 2131 MPa). The VACNTs growth has a significant effect on the elongation at break, which is 250% higher for the nanostructured bundles (4.2 %) than that in the non-treated bundles (1.2%). The presence of the VACNTs may generate fibre-to-fibre frictional forces inside the bundle and an inhomogeneous elongation of the filaments during the tensile tests. The resulting value of Young's modulus shows an important decrease for all the treatments (SiO₂ deposition: -26%, desizing: -32%, VACNTs growth: -44% for strain interval from 0.2 % to 0.4%).

The analysis of the fibre bundle tensile test should however be taken with caution in the case of the VACNT growth bundles, since the addition of the CNT forest challenges the assumption of non-friction between fibres. The fibre bundles are also non homogeneous since the CNT are present only on the periphery of the fibre tow and complicates the accurate measurement of the fibre diameter. Tensile testing of composite samples should be able to verify the observation made of the effect of VACNT growth on the fibre's tensile modulus. The storage modulus E' of the composite specimens [GPa] is calculated from the following equation (2) where K is the stiffness [N.m⁻¹] of the specimen, F_c is an adjustment factor associated with the sample geometry [m⁻¹], H is the test length [m], S_e is the acted surface [m²] and δ is the phase lag. The calculated storage modulus of the different specimens is reported in the Figure 6.

$$E' = K \cdot F_c \cdot \frac{H}{S_e} \cdot \cos \delta \quad (2)$$

The VACNTs interlaminar inclusion in the composite specimens with $\pm 45^\circ$ fibres orientation results in an increase of 12% the storage modulus compared to the no-treated specimen (from 7.10 to 7.91 GPa). The interlaminar occupation of the VACNTs forest in contact with both resin and carbon fabric phases (see Figure 3) efficiently increases the stiffness, although the nanostructuration has a negative effect on the Young’s modulus of carbon fibre bundles. The decrease of 20% of the storage modulus (7.1 to 5.66) for the SiO₂ pre-treated composite samples is consistent with their weight loss (Table 3) and resulting decreased fibre volume fraction.

Figure 5: Young's modulus of the carbon filaments for different specimen treatments
(Bundle tensile tests)

Figure 6: Storage modulus of composite specimens with different treatments
(DMA tests)

3 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The mechanical effects of the VACNTs growth on carbon fibres were investigated via bundle tensile tests and DMA tests. The results are briefly summarized:

- 1) The nanostructuring of fibre bundles has a positive effect on their elongation at break, but also decreases the tensile strength and the Young's modulus by generating fibre-to-fibre frictional forces.
- 2) The interlaminar inclusion of VACNTs in carbon/epoxy composite samples increases the storage modulus compared to no treated composites.

Further tests, including traction, 3 point bending, and double cantilever will provide additional details on the effects of the nanostructuring on the mechanical properties of the composites and will pave the way to future ballistic tests.

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